

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Refining the set of KPI for quality assurance of the project
Deliverable number	D4 (Del. Rel. No. D1.3)
Revision	0
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	30/04/2022
Actual date of issue	30/04/2022
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MPI-M
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This document is a report on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which shall serve as a quality assurance of the project.

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1 Executive summary

Six Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined for quality control of the implementation of nextGEMS. These KPI's provide a management tool to assess progress and changes, both qualitatively and quantitatively. At the beginning of the project, we refine the six proposed KPIs and detail the implementation plan in this Deliverable. During the project lifetime the KPIs will be continuously reflected and updated, in the Deliverables D1.4 and D1.5, as well as in the interim technical reports.

2 Conclusion & Results

As the KPIs are a living process, they will evolve along the project. Milestones (MS) were partly attributed as KPI targets.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	yes
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	yes
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Methodology

To manage the risk and to measure the nextGEMS success in meeting its objectives (see Section 3) and realizing its desired impact six *Key Performance Indicators* (KPIs), prescribed as K1-K6 in Section 4.2, have been defined.

These KPI's provide a management tool to assess progress and changes, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Thus the first three KPIs are tracking the effectiveness of the Hackathons by virtue of their results. 22 Milestones (MS) were, following standard practice, identified with tasks or achievements which nextGEMS as a whole relies on (see Annex 1 - Description of Action (Part A), 1.3.4. *WT4 List of milestones*, p.60). They will be regularly assessed, at nextGEMS Executive Board meetings (NEB meetings), e.g., in the framework of Hackathons, and refined or changed as the need arises. Focusing on a small number of KPIs and milestones is part of the project management strategy, our experience has been that maintaining a focus on a small number of truly crucial KPIs and milestones, is essential for keeping a large multi-institutional project on track. The management team will provide separate Deliverables on KPI's for the mid-project stock-taking in month 19 (D1.4), and again to conclude the results in month 47 as the project is coming to its end (D1.5). Briefing on KPI's will also be included in the periodic technical reporting.

4.2 Refinement and Implementation of the KPIs

This section will refine and describe the planned implementation of the KPIs. For refining the KPIs we use the SMART criteria through making our targets

- **Specific**, by allocating milestones to KPI targets

- **M**easurable, by attributing numbers to quantitative KPIs,
- **A**ttainable,
- **R**elevant, and
- **T**ime-bound by refining per project year

Future reports on KPIs can rely and supplement on the following tables. The tables describe for each KPI the planned implementation and gives specificity to the refined success indicators. Also, we provide details on first achievements within the comments section to each KPI.

Based on discussions with project scientists, we'd like to include here some general comments and critique on some KPIs. The KPIs 1 and 2 measure the technical and physical maturity of both SR-ESMs. While it is seemingly an easy task to add numbers to both KPIs in form of simulated days per day (SDPD) for the throughput and W/m^2 for example for the energy leak in the models, those numbers have strong dependencies on the machine architecture or the tuning of the models. We therefore set one overall upper bound that we want to stay below in all development Cycles as well as the production runs.

KPI 3 and partly 4 are *qualitative* success indicators with some quantitative statistics in form of organized events. However, their real success will be measured by products resulting out of co-production activities in KPI 3 and our ability to include and train as many early-stage researchers (ESR) as possible within and between our hackathons following the nextGEMS training strategy. KPIs 5 and 6 are again of a *quantitative* nature with numbers of Vlog entries and published papers / conference talks in KPI 5 and conducted surveys and their results on project internal collaboration in KPI 6. Details follow in tables 3 to 11.

K1	Technical maturity of the Storm-resolving Earth System models (SR-ESMs)			
Description	Simulating days-per-day (SDPD) in throughput at the target (2.5km) and twice the target solution, achieving at least 0.2 simulation years/day including I/O on a fraction of the expected availability of computing resources for the production simulations.			
Method	Quantitative			
Related WPs	WP1, WP2, WP3			
Lead Responsible	EMCWF, MPI-M			
Planned Implementation	We are keeping track of the model performance in terms of SDPD when implementing new features in the different development cycles, as well as when improving model output or moving to new supercomputers.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	Set up of analysis workflows (MS4); High frequency data logging implemented (MS5)	Cycle 2 Runs finished and documented (MS6); Start of Production Runs (MS11)	Production Runs finished (MS15)	Recommendations for pathways to further improve ESMs (MS21)
Status	completed			
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We've set up an analysis Wiki describing the workflow (MS4). The Wiki is called easy.gems, is publicly available and includes information on the Cycle 1 simulations as well as on how to best load and process the model output (see also deliverable D2.1). • The high-frequency logging in IFS and ICON was implemented (MS5). The technical details are described in the deliverable D8.3. It is part of the new features in the currently running Cycle 2 simulations. • Cycle 1: in the Cycle 1 simulations IFS had a throughput of about 40 SDPD (4 km) and ICON 17 SDPD (5 km) • Cycle 2 (in progress): preliminary numbers are 50 SDPD for IFS (432nodes x 128 cores) and 80 SDPD for ICON (400 nodes x 128 cores). The numbers strongly depend on the finally chosen time step, the used machine, and the available nodes. 			

Table 3: Description of KPI K1.

K2	Physical readiness of the two SR-ESMs			
Description	Assessment of the stability and quality of the coupled simulations over multi annual timescales, using a small set of metrics, e.g., sea-surface temperatures, top-of-atmosphere radiation, land surface temperatures to be within acceptable deviations from observed or reanalysis records.			
Method	Quantitative			
Related WPs	WP2			
Lead Responsible	ECMWF			
Planned Implementation	The first half of the project serves the development in SR-ESMs. After the readiness review of the model in month 18, the model shall be applied and tailored for stakeholders and users needs.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	First evaluation of Cycle 1 simulations; Cycle 2 Runs (MS6)	Cycle 3 Runs	<i>- Application Phase -</i>	
Status	Cycle 1 completed Cycle 2 running			
Further comments	Relevant achievements evaluating Cycle 1 simulations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a non-closing water and energy budget in the IFS model was detected and fixed • a intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ) stuck at the equator with a too warm sea surface temperature and a decoupling of the mixed layer of the ocean was detected and respective model components changed for the Cycle 2 simulations • an energy leak in the atmosphere in the ICON model was detected and partly fixed. Further improvements will be the task for the CYcle 2 hackathon. 			

Table 4: Description of KPI K2.

K3	Cultural indicator			
Description	Assessing how well modeling and application teams succeed in guiding the Knowledge Coproduction component of Hackathons to deliver products through Challenge Problems			
Method	Qualitative			
Related WPs	WP1, WP10			
Lead Responsible	BSC			
Planned Implementation	Within the six planned hackathons, WP 10 will evaluate and analyse the Knowledge Coproduction between scientists and stakeholders. The project will confront itself with 'real-world' scientific and societal questions developed together with stakeholders (Challenge Problems). Internal surveys involving at least half of the nextGEMS scientists will be used to assess the success of Knowledge Coproduction.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	Organization of Cycle 1 (PI) Hackathon (MS2); Organization of Cycle 2 Hackathon (MS9)	Challenge Problem Success (MS8); Progress briefing about links to IAMS (MS10); Organization of Cycle 3 Hackathon (MS12)	Organization of climate change and renewable energy hackathon (MS19)	Organization of ocean climate change hackathon (MS20); Organization of Hazarthon (MS22)
Status	Cycle 1 done Cycle 2 ongoing			
Further comments	Relevant achievements since project start: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> in the Cycle 1 hackathon we started the Knowledge Coproduction component on solar energy with our project partner IBERDROLA resulting in new implementation in the two models and plans for respective challenges to work on in the Cycle 2 hackathon. 			

Table 5: Description of KPI K3.

K3	Cultural indicator
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• the Storms&Society theme conducted a Social Network Analysis (SNA) at which they analysed the interaction between participants in the Cycle 1 hackathon. They will continue the SNA also at all following hackathons to investigate the change.• in preparation to the Cycle 2 hackathon we invited many further stakeholders from the solar- and wind energy sector for an exchange of knowledge and interest that helped shape our Challenge Problem for the Cycle 2 hackathon.• included nextGEMS stakeholder groups were <i>scientists</i> and <i>technologists</i> in the Cycle 1 hackathon. For the Cycle 2 hackathon we plan to extend the groups to include <i>users</i> from renewable energy and <i>policy-makers</i>.

Table 6: Continuation of description of KPI K3.

K4	nextGEMS contribution to Early-Stage-Researcher (ESR) development			
Description	Measured by two sub-indicators: With at least two nextGEMS post-docs taking leadership roles in project activities and regular participation of several outside early career researchers in each of the Hackathons.			
Method	Qualitative and Quantitative			
Related WPs	All WPs			
Lead Responsible	MPI-M			
Planned Implementation	An ESR representative will be elected. Next to communicating their problems to the NAB, the ESR representative also organizes ESR activities together with the project office. For each hackathon, external ESRs have the opportunity to apply for 15 stipends in total and get invited to join the hackathons. In addition, each PI will send one or two representatives to do hand-on research in the hackathons. During the project lifetime, where applicable, nextGEMS partners will offer job opportunities within the project's research fields.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	Support of internal ESRs by involving them in project activities and communication; promoting up to 15 external ESRs in each hackathon.			
Status	achieved for the Cycle 2 hackathon			
Further comments	Relevant achievements since project start: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the Cycle 1 hackathon took place in month 2 of the project in between Covid lockdowns and therefore didn't provide time for planning and offering stipends. Instead, many PhDs and PostDocs from the PIs research groups joined the hackathon and helped analyzing the model output. During the Cycle 1 hackathon the project scientist and PostDoc Divya Praturi was elected as ESR representative. for the Cycle 2 hackathon we selected 15 external ESR at the Master and PhD level with a renewable energy or climate modelling background. They will join us in the hackathon and work on a Challenge Problem related to renewable energy. 			

Table 7: Description of KPI K4.

K4	nextGEMS contribution to Early-Stage-Researcher (ESR) development
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• during the Cycle 2 hackathon the ESR representative and the project office together planned an ESR event with a strong socializing component.• two nextGEMS PostDocs have already taken up leadership roles by organizing and running the IFS Cycle 2 simulations.• within our weekly nextGEMS Office Hour internal ESRs are encouraged to share their work and results

Table 8: Continuation of description of KPI K4.

K5	Dissemination and communication activities			
Description	One, that all 6 NextGEMS stakeholder target groups have been reached and meaningfully engaged; the second, by actively involving at least two thirds of NextGEMS scientists in communication or dissemination activities.			
Method	Quantitative			
Related WPs	WP1, WP10, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9			
Lead Responsible	BSC, MPI-M			
Planned Implementation	nextGEMS will use a web-based multi-media platform presenting various forms of content along an easy-to-follow timeline designed to target nextGEMS stakeholders. nextGEMS scientists will get involved in Vlogs as <i>Science Explainers</i> , where they will describe their research in plain language for stakeholders. Continuously check, reflect and improve the planned Dissemination and Communication activities that are listed in Annex 1 - Description of Action (Part B), <i>Table 2.2</i> , p.22.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	Website online (MS1); Vlog debuts (MS3); two involved stakeholder groups	Scientists as Communicators (MS7) training; five <i>Science Explainers</i> recorded; four involved stakeholder groups; first model output datasets openly shared	First findings and model outputs presented on Vlogs (MS13, MS16, MS17); five involved stakeholder groups; first project scientific papers published	nextGEMS results video (MS18); six involved stakeholder groups
Status	Achieved			
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • together with a web agency we've created an attractive and modern web presence at https://nextgems-h2020.eu/ • We started our Vlog with eight project and theme overview videos recorded before and during the Cycle 1 hackathon. • in the Cycle 1 hackathon, two out of six stakeholder groups have been involved, in the upcoming Cycle 2 hackathon four stakeholder groups will be involved. 			

Table 9: Description of KPI K5.

K5	Dissemination and communication activities
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • first publications in peer-reviewed journals are being prepared. Participation in conferences becomes possible again with the COVID-situation improving

Table 10: Continued description of KPI K5.

K6	Internal processes			
Description	Assessing how effectively WPs are functioning and by the management team interviewing a small set of scientists from each of the WPs to assess their satisfaction with the project and publishing actions as relevant that follow-up on the interviews.			
Method	Qualitative and Quantitative			
Related WPs	all WPs			
Lead Responsible	MPI-M			
Planned Implementation	The management team will prepare one to two surveys for the mid and the end of the project duration, about the progress and the researchers current state of satisfaction within the WPs. Additionally, interviews will be held on a randomly selected set of scientists. An overall evaluation shall summarize important findings.			
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
KPI Targets (Related MSs)	N/A	First survey and interviews	NAB mid-term feedback (MS14)	Second survey and an overall evaluation of the internal processes.
Status	—			
Further comments	<p>Relevant achievements since project start:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a first survey after the Cycle 1 hackathon showed an active participation of project scientists from all research themes. The majority of scientists were very satisfied with the start of the project and it's first meeting in month 2. 			

Table 11: Description of KPI K6.

5 References (Bibliography)

None.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

We will upload the document on our website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/partner-area/> in the section *Partner Area*. However, we consider KPIs as a management tool and therefore most important to the project office, the consortium members and the Commission service.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There is a link to the upcoming deliverable D1.4 "First report on KPI for quality assurance of the project" as well as to D1.5 "Second report on KPI for quality assurance of the project".

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu> online
- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - Activity: NextCalendArt 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.-3.4.2022 near Madrid
- weekly Office Hours for internal communication and dissemination on topics such as (i) current state of IFS and ICON developments, (ii) Knowledge Coproduction with the solar energy industry, (iii) data handling with *intake*, and many more.

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.